

SOIL RECLAMATION

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Abstract. This article talks about soil reclamation and its improvement. The further development of land reclamation will also briefly touch on our attitude to the problems we face today.

Keywords. Land, irrigated soil, reclamation, irrigation, agrotechnology, agriculture, land fund

Enter. In the strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev on modernization and rapid development of agriculture, deepening of structural changes and consistent development of agricultural production, further strengthening of the country's food security, production of environmentally friendly products to expand, significantly increase the export potential of the agrarian sector, further improve the melioration of irrigated land, develop networks of melioration and irrigation objects, introduce intensive methods into the agricultural production sector, first of all, modern agro-technologies that save water and resources, with high productivity use of agricultural machinery; The measures to take systematic measures to mitigate the negative impact of global climate changes and the formation of the Aral Sea on agricultural development and the life activities of the population are mentioned. Lands used in agriculture, especially irrigated the lands are unquestionable

it is a priceless treasure and an important source of living conditions of all peoples. Reasonable and efficient use of these lands, expansion of the land fund has always been the main issue for mankind. This is especially reflected in the continuous growth of the population and the demand for food products. According to the information of FAO and UNESCO, during the last half-century, the world population has increased by 3 billion. from 6.4 billion It is not difficult to understand how valuable this land is to mankind, despite the increase of 400,000,000,000,000.00. Land is a finite and non-renewable natural resource. Today, its salinization, desertification, irrigation and wind erosion, pollution of the soil with various technical wastes, depletion of humus and nutrient elements pose a serious threat to this resource.. According to the accepted definition in the science of melioration, agricultural melioration is the successful development of reserve land, the rapid increase of soil fertility, its protection, and the provision of high yields from agricultural crops. consists of a system of activities aimed at fundamentally improving the natural conditions of the area unfavorable for agriculture. The main tasks of land reclamation in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, are to prevent soil salinization and swamping and to fight against these processes, to develop dry land, to fight against water and wind erosion, to recultivate land, to reduce soil compaction and humus content. (degumification) prevention, the fight against soil pollution and

desertification and other negative processes is the main goal. The systems of melioration activities are different for regions with different natural conditions, and the development of these activities requires deep knowledge of the genesis of soils and their properties. The enormous importance of soil reclamation problems in the economy and the collection of extensive data on solving this multifaceted problem became the basis for the separation of soil reclamation science from the science of soil science, which is an undesirable, negative process that occurs on land used for agriculture. Research in learning is characterized by special tasks and methods.

The main task of land reclamation is land reclamation and development of land reclamation measures to increase production capacities and completely eliminate negative and undesirable processes occurring in the soil. It is divided into 3 main categories according to the goals of improvement. Reclamation of lands with an unfavorable water regime (irrigation of arid agricultural regions, drainage of water in over-flooded lands, discharge of water to pastures in desert and semi-desert areas with developed cattle breeding, etc.); reclamation of lands with unfavorable physical and chemical properties (salty, sandy, heavy, berchy, compacted soils, etc.); Reclamation of lands eroded by water and wind. Reclamation by means and methods of influencing adverse natural conditions. are divided into the following types: hydrotechnical melioration, forestry melioration (elimination of soil erosion caused by wind and water with measures such as the establishment of surrounding forests and the establishment of special anti-erosion trees). long-term structures that provide water in the required amount and in the required period. Land reclamation, especially in dry climate regions, also leads to climate change, as irrigation increases humidity in the near-ground layer of the air (due to evaporation from the soil and vegetation), resulting in lower temperatures and less droughts. Reclamation is capital-intensive, but it is reclamation it pays for itself in a few years due to annual increase in land productivity. For example, grain crops yield 4-5 times more on irrigated land than on non-irrigated land, and it is practically impossible to grow some crops without irrigation in irrigated agricultural areas. providing the population of Kurrami with food and other agricultural products, and secondly, due to the development of industry, the improvement of the melioration capacity of mankind, the development of many new lands, the expansion of cultivated areas, and the melioration of irrigated lands perceived as needing improvement. In our country, more than 95% of the total products obtained from agricultural crops are delivered on land areas that are being meliorated and irrigated. Therefore, further expansion of irrigated arable land areas, increasing soil fertility by improving their land reclamation remains one of the main urgent tasks of our time. However, it is important to pay attention to one thing: 75% of the land to be developed is saline, and all irrigated land is re-salinated or prone to salinization. Many such examples can be cited, but despite this, we are obliged to improve the land reclamation and increase its productivity. Therefore, in order to solve any problem related to soil reclamation, raising the ecological consciousness of our people and training highly educated specialists should be one of the main urgent tasks of the current era.

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